

JAIN JOURNAL

ISSN : 0021 4043

Vol. LIII, No. I-IV

2018-2019

pp. 68-72

Environmental degradation and its impact on Jainism

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Abstract

Jainism is one of the most significant, heterodox and oldest religions, not only in India but also in the world which proposed the principles of ecology and conservation of environment. The Jainism considers that we must have an awareness of the holy tie between human being and environment which is necessary for our planet and its health as well as the survival of flora and fauna. Everything that surrounds us collectively forms the environment. The air, the soil, the water, the rivers, the mountains, the plants, the animals, in short, all living and non-living things around, comprises the environment, which has influenced and shaped lives since the time immemorial. The environment constitutes a life support system for all beings. Through a process of natural selection and elimination, it is the environment that has directed the evolution of the biosphere, as it exists today. Therefore, we must not deprive our mother earth from its resources with misusing, draining and polluting it.

Introduction

There is a Jain parable that demonstrates that even animals, which are on a lower level of evolution than man, exhibit qualities of compassion for fellow beings and concern for environment. Man, despite his superior brain, is lacking in wisdom exhibited by animals. However, primitive man did not look upon nature with indifference and arrogance. That is a modern

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It is interesting to compare Jaina philosophy with classical physics as well as quantum physics. Both swear by objectivity, rationality and empiricism. However unlike quantum physics, Jaina Philosophy contains transcendental topic such as rebirth and doctrine of *karma*. This is exactly why Jaina *anekānta* cannot be called hard science. Although, *Anekānta* is a broad philosophy. *Syādvāda* has a social dimension. This philosophy leads one to tolerance and ahimsa or non-violence. Apart from its philosophical and ethical values and in spite of its different historical and cultural moorings, *Syādvāda* had rich scientific potential which, however, remained unrealized for thousands of years. It was well ahead of its time in this respect.

Reference

1. Das Gupta, S. N. *A History of Indian Philosophy*, vol-I (1922) Cambridge Univ. Press.
2. Mookerjee, Satkari *The Jaina Philosophy of Non-absolutism* (1944), Bharati Jaina Parisad, Calcutta.
3. Bergmann, Peter Gabriel *Introduction to the Theory of Relativity* (1969), Prentice-Hall, New Delhi
4. Mattews, P.T. *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics* (1968), Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi.
5. Rajam, J.B. *Atomic Physics* (1960), S. Chand & Co, New Delhi
6. Shah, N. J. *Jaina Theory of Multiple facts of Reality and Truth (Anekāntavāda)*, (2000), Motilal Banarsidass, New Delhi
7. Sikdar, J.C. *Concept of Matter in Jaina Philosophy*, (1990), Parsvanatha Vidyapitha, Varanasi.

attitude that developed gradually as man became more socialized and knowledgeable. In the beginning of the world, there was harmony. The laws and rules of the nature guided every being on the earth. The primitive man, who was a wanderer too, lived in co-existence with nature and his fellow beings. Six thousand and five hundred years ago, man learnt the art of cultivation of crops. He began to settle down and live in societies. Yet, his needs were limited. However, gradually the need was replaced by greed. The more civilized he became, the more selfish he grew. He exploited natural and human resources to satisfy his own desire and hence qualities like violence, hatred, lust, acquisitiveness, etc. began to replace humanitarian values like co-existence, compassion and non-violence. The logical result of this erroneous attitude is evident in the environmental degradation of mind boggling magnitude we are facing at all levels today.

Environmental degradation and its impact

Physical degradation is reflected in ozone depletion, drying up of lakes, scarcity of clean drinking water, deforestation, pollution, increase in the occurrence of natural calamities, global warming, spread of epidemic diseases, increase of non-cultivable lands, soil erosion, etc. This is due to overexploitation of nature by man.

On the socio-economic level, degradation is reflected as population explosion, economic and social inequalities, poverty, unemployment, unfair trade practices, discrimination based on caste, creed, gender, etc. These differences and conflicts arise due to adherence to false system of values that teach unhealthy competition and not co-existence.

The rising number of suicides, individual dissatisfactions, chronic anxiety, depression, stress, mental illnesses, rising insecurities etc. are indications of the psychological degradation.

Power struggles, corruption among leaders of the country, lack of concern for the welfare of the public, international border disputes, bribery, terrorism, etc. are indications of political degradation. Politicians and bureaucrats, who have to serve the people, are channeling public's money

for their personal uses. The richer nations are exploiting the vulnerabilities of weaker nations and their resources to gain more profits.

Religion, which is supposed to guide people on the right path, is being misinterpreted and has become a cause for wars and massacres. There are fights among the mankind over the differences in religions. Anti-nature rituals, performed in the name of religion and God, are causing pollution and damage to the environment. Worst of all is corruption, exploitation and inhuman attitude in the basic area of health, education and judiciary.

Environment - Religious and Scientific Perspectives

Most of world's religions believe that nature is God's creation. Our ancestors worshipped nature in its myriad forms - the sun, wind, rain, rivers, etc. However, though people preached worshipping nature, they did not spare much thought to its preservation. And now they have begun to worship God who is protected in stone buildings. But what we need is not worshipping of nature, rather living with nature. The irony is, modern man is neither worshipping nor living with nature. Instead, he is making the nature obedient to his greed and materialistic comforts. Hence, environment, at all levels, is in the midst of degradation. The need of the hour is the protection and preservation of environment from further degradation. The only inherent religion of mankind is compassion, love and co-existence and any preaching or practice in the name of religion that does not include the above aspects is not a religion at all. Religion misunderstood in practice and misinterpreted in the pretext of scientific temper is what exists today. It is time, we seriously reflect on the words of Albert Einstein; "*Science without religion is lame and religion without science is blind!*" Jainism is one such religion that establishes scientifically a deep inter-relationship between environment and man, and spiritually provides a framework to realize and live the same. It is crucial that we introspect on how to adapt religious teachings to the task of revaluing nature so as to prevent its degradation. As Thomas Berry has aptly pointed out, "*What is necessary is the comprehensive re-*

evaluation of human-earth relation, if the human is to continue as a viable species on an increasingly degraded planet". So, one of the greatest challenges to existing religions is how to respond to environmental degradation. The critical question of both justice and survival is how to pull back from this disastrous situation and remake our relation with each other and with the mother Earth. In a world with man as the crown of evolution and thus creation, environmental degradation has soared sky-high. Why did this happen? We have to ponder upon which takes precedence - whether it is environment and man or man and environment. Earlier, all that surrounded man was environment; today it is man who is surrounding everything.

Conclusion

To resolve the crisis, we do have innumerable policies, projects, laws and regulations to protect our environment. But as these laws and regulations increase, so does violence and pollution, because we are erring in our approach to the solution for the problems. Without targeting self-purity, no environmental blessedness can be achieved to restore harmony, co-existence and peace. And to realize this, we need religion of non-violence, compassion and peaceful co-existence. In addition, the religion should also have the principle of scientific vision, spiritual mission and religious consciousness. Of course, all religions have their own way of contributing to the welfare of mankind, but Jainism can contribute in a greater magnitude in understanding the environmental degradation under three unique scientific approaches: (i) The concept of God and the theory of Universe, (ii) The Jaina ethics, particularly *Aticāras* analyzed under *Anuvrata*, *Guṇavratas* and *Sikṣāvratas* and (iii) Jaina doctrine of *Karma Theory*. Jaina religion itself is a religion of environment. Jainism brings all three aspects - man, nature and environment under the umbrella of co-existence with nature. The Jaina message is simple - it is not man and nature rather it is man with nature. If nature has to take its own course, it goes by natural selection. But man's intervention has caused chaos in natural selection. So man, the thinking animal, should balance body and mind to maintain the balance in environment.

Acknowledgement

The author sincerely acknowledges Dr. Geetha Ramanujam, Department of Jainology, University of Madras, for her book "*Environmental awareness in Jainism*" for writing this article.

References

1. J.Jaini, *The Outlines of Jainism* (Cambridge University Press, 1916), p.47.
2. D.K. Asthana and M. Asthana, *Environment, Problems and Solutions*, (New Delhi, S. Chand Company Ltd, 2001), pp.18
3. L. White, Jr., *The Historical Roots of our Ecological Crisis*, Science, 155, (March 1967), p.1204.
4. T. Berry, *Hinduism and Ecology*, edited by C.K. Chapple and M.E. Tucker, (Harvard Divinity School, 2000), p.xxv
5. C.K. Chapple, *Non-violence to Animals, Earth, and Self in Asian Traditions*, (State University of New York, 1993), pp.12-13.
6. A. Beasant, *Seven Great Religions*, (Madras, Theosophical Publishing House, 1985), pp. 197-235.
7. S. Jain and S. Pandey, *Jainism in a Global Perspective*, (Varanasi, Parsvanatha Vidyapita, 1998), p. 163.